

Human and Nature Relationship in the Novel *Jaya*

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Abstract

Ancient Hindu teachings present nature as a deity and emphasize the notion that human adoration of the natural world and respect for all living things have maintained ecological balance. The natural world has long been worshipped as a deity. From many literary to philosophical texts, nature worship has preserved the balance of the ecosystem and highlights the damage done to it. Environmental ethics often contain teachings about dharma and righteousness which include responsibilities towards nature and the environment can explore how these texts contribute to the development of an environment in Indian culture. This paper explores the eco-critical aspects found in the novel “Jaya: an Illustrated Retelling of Mahabharata”. The novel offers a multifaceted exploration of human-nature relationships it promotes the idea that humans have a moral and ethical duty to respect, protect and live in harmony with nature.

Keywords: Eco-Criticism, Retelling of *Mahabharata*, Human-Nature, Environment ethics.

Introduction

The Mahabharata one of the major ancient Sanskrit epics of India offers profound insights into the human nature relationship through its narrative characters and ethical teachings. The contemporary retelling of Mahabharata, *Jaya: an Illustrated Retelling of Mahabharata* written by Devdutt Pattanaik incorporates the same characters and teaching from the ancient text. In the article *Ecological Aspects in Indian Epics: An ecocritical Study of Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni’s ‘The Palace of Illusion’* written by Anjali Priya states:

In the Hindu tradition, the epics and Puranas have given a detailed description of periodic and cyclic destruction of the world. The decline of virtue and behaviour at the end of each aeon would bring the world to a deplorable condition.” (183)

Ecocriticism is a literary and cultural theory that emerged in the late 20th century. It focuses on the relationship between literature and the environment. It also explains how literary work reflects and influences our understanding of nature ecology and environmental issues. Ecocritics analyse the text to uncover environmental themes, attitudes towards nature and how literature can both shape and be shaped by environmental consciousness. Tamil poets have also pointed out the importance of natural environment in the past. For example, Uma Ramamoorthy says:

The poets fill the poems of “Akam” by getting tint and colour from Nature and have made their poems produce everlasting interest not only to man’s life but

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also to Nature, itself. Wordsworth's observation, "The world is too much with us" absolutely reflects the perceptions of "Akam" poets. (Uma Ramamoorthy 95)
In *A New Approach to Literary Theory and Criticism* Ecocriticism is summed up as follows:

- It is a reading of a literary text which incorporates environmental concerns and issues. The ecocritics, in their attempts to bring environmental issues into focus, re-read major literary works and pay special attention to the representation of nature. In doing so, they go by concepts like growth, energy, balance and symbiosis.
- The ecocritics also wish to find out what role has the physical-geographical setting played in the structure of a poem or a novel. (Malik and Batra, 163)

In the Retelling of *Mahabharata*, *Jaya* describes the dynastic conflict for the control of Hastinapur, which culminated in the epic Kurukshetra War. It is primarily a work of epic mythology and history, but it also includes philosophical lessons and considerations of morality. The handling of environmental concerns in *Jaya* and how it contributes to the boundary between ecology and literature can be better understood by including ecocriticism in the study of the novel. The novel reveals severe environmental issues, conveys a profound philosophical message, and is still relevant today. The modern era is proof of the dangers that environmental deterioration poses to the whole human species.

Human culture has a reciprocal relationship with the physical world. Ecocriticism plays an important role in empowering the world's ecological vision. Environmental problems can be solved only when a serious deliberation about them takes place" (Priya, 182)

The novel *Jaya*, emphasizes the importance of respecting and living in harmony with nature. The characters in the novel are often depicted as having a deep reverence for the natural world. In the Tamil version *Villibharatham* written by Villiputturar, Hastinapur is depicted with natural sceneries.

The evening view of Athinapuratran was like the sun that is visible throughout the day does not fall on the lotus flower clusters in the pool of light, and the goddesses were spread out so that the sunlight did not fall on them, because the day was waning. (Mahila 113)

Nature is glorified everywhere. For example, during the exile, Pandavas live in the forest where they interact with Sages, animals and plants demonstrating a symbiotic relationship with nature. The novel also encloses a description of the natural world such as forests, rivers and mountains. The forest plays a significant role in *Jaya* serving as a setting where the characters undergo personal and spiritual transformations. It is in the forest that they learn important life lessons connect with their inner self and gain wisdom from the natural world. The concept of Dharma is central to the characters with ethical dilemmas related to their responsibilities towards society, family and nature. The novel undergoes the idea that humans have a duty not only to teach others but also to the environment. This duty includes protecting forests and preserving the balance of nature. The forest takes centre stage in *Jaya*'s eleventh Chapter "Exile". After losing everything, the Pandavas and Draupadi remain in the wilderness. To recover what has been lost in life, one must give themselves over to nature. "Forest has become the space for serious philosophical deliberations and many of life's mysteries become comprehensible during the stay in woods" (Mandal, 4), Draupadi gave

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herself up to a tree and revealed all she had been keeping hidden in her heart. This helps her achieve a strong position of chastity.

The tree boomed, ‘If you were truly chaste, Draupadi, you could have done it with the power of your chastity’ . . . Draupadi broke down . . . ‘I love Karna. I regret . . . Having revealed the truth of her heart, Draupadi had been cleansed. (Jaya, 183-184)

Throughout the novel, various sages and hermits provide wisdom and guidance to the characters. These sages often live in harmony with nature and their teaching emphasizes the importance of balance moderation and Environmental Stewardship. “Just as Shiva teaches Arjuna, Hanuman teaches Bhima a lesson in humility. The forest transforms the Pandavas and makes them better kings. The tragedy of exile thus seems very much part of a divine plan to help men be better rulers.” (Jaya, 182)

The Novel features various animals and natural deities. These entities are not mere literary devices but are seen as integral parts of the world. Characters often seek guidance from animals and nature spirits reinforcing the idea that humans are interconnected with the natural world. The depiction of hunting animals, especially Deer is seen in both the epic Ramayana and Mahabharata. They hunt the animals for various purposes. In *Jaya*, during the Pandava's stay at Dwaita-Vana, they hunt deer and give it to Rishi for yagnas. As a consequence of killing so many animals one day Yudhistira gets a dream, where a deer pleases him to leave the forest as they have killed many of their fellow beings.

Yudhistira, one day, had a dream. He saw a deer weeping, begging him to leave the forest and return to where he came from. ‘In all these years, you and your brothers have hunted down so many of us that our numbers have dwindled. Please go back . . . Leave Dwaita-vana.’ (Jaya, 188)

This Specific sight illustrates how guilty human feels about destroying the forest. In the current situation, this is accurate. Man destroys the forest and the ecosystem for his peaceful existence. The appeal made by deer to Yudhistira can be compared to the silent cry of the animals for liberation from man, who is destroying the forest and utilising animals for scientific study. “During their exile, Pandavas thoughtlessly used forest resources for their survival. Anthropocentrism is also reflected in the novel, when Draupadi relates how Nakula and Sahadeva brought fawns for her to pet, without any regret of separating the newborn from its mother” (Priya, 183). In the end, Draupadi’s sons will have a terrible death. This acts as a lesson for the readers not to harm nature as it will come back to them in a worse manner. It is a sign of warning to human not to hurt animals for their selfish pleasures. The novel encourages taking responsibility for their action and their impact on the natural world. It suggests that humans should strive for a harmonious co-existence with nature rather than exploiting it for personal gain. “Humans exploit flora for sustenance and shelter while they kill wildlife for sports, food, clothing, and many other purposes.” (Praveena, 443) in the novel *Jaya*, Pandavas bring golden lotus for Draupadi. They are not concerned much about the flora of the forest. They were ready to do anything that made Draupadi happy.

Bhima reached the lake where he found hundreds of fragrant golden lotuses. As he began plucking them for Draupadi, he was attacked by the Gandharvas who guarded the lake. Bhima swatted them aside as if they were mosquitoes and

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continued collecting the flowers. He then returned to where his brothers were with a huge bunch of flowers that Draupadi was delighted to receive. (Jaya, 182)

The novel also exposes the consequences of human actions on the environment. It serves as a cautionary tale, highlighting the destructive consequence of disregarding nature and pursuing unchecked desires. On our planet, deforestation is rising daily. The effects of clearing the forest were represented in an ancient epic. The devastation of the Khandava forest has been used as a metaphor for two things: first, it shows how superior man is to nature, and second, it illustrates how destroying nature would ultimately lead to the extinction of humankind.

In *Jaya*, Krishna asks Arjuna ‘Can anyone establish a field or an orchard or a garden or a city without destroying a forest?’ asked Krishna. The human wanted to rule the land without leaving any creature alive. They burnt down everything. “The trees, the herbs, the shrubs, every tiny blade of grass” was burning (*Jaya*, 111) Man has thought that he is superior to nature but nature always proved back to man it is powerful. The cry of the creatures was not taken seriously by man. Their desire becomes more important. “The birds and beasts cried out and tried to escape the flames. ‘Kill them all’, said Krishna . . . so that no one returns to claim the land you claim to be yours. Know the price of ownership.” (*Jaya*, 112) The aforementioned example serves as a reminder that even in cases where it would be morally acceptable to do so, a virtuous person would refrain from committing damage to another living being. The modern age, however, has seen humanity destroying nature for their needs. As a consequence, Arjuna faces many problems in his life. He leaves his mother and goes into the wilderness for thirteen years. It is obvious from the fact that Krishna was wounded by a hunter’s arrow that nature will exact revenge and heal itself no matter who did the damage.

There is a self contained, peaceful, sylvan civilisation in harmony with nature. Khandav van is set afire by Arjun and Krishna Vasudev as coveted by Agni. Even when consented to in an inebriated state this act of Arjun and Krishna Vasudev is a willing act, a matter of choice. And from this choice consequences will follow inevitably and severally. (Mandal, 66)

As he states every human who is harming nature must endure hardship in life. One must live in peace with nature by building it and protecting it. Harming will lead to the destruction of own self.

Analyzing the relationships between characters and nature in these epics can reveal cultural attitudes towards the natural world. For example, the Pandava's exile in the Mahabharata demonstrates various aspects of human-nature relationships. Indian epics are a fantastic resource for learning about how people and the environment interact. The Mahabharata has been retold in modern times, but all of them have completely adhered to the Veda Vyasa’s original plot. The *Jaya*’s primary characters are created by nature. When it comes to the Pandavas, Bhisma is the son of the Ganga River, Karna is the son of Surya (the Sun God), Bhima is the son of Vayu (the God of Wind), Arjuna is the son of Indra (the God of Rain), and Draupadi is born out of fire. To demonstrate how all of nature will come together to form a family, the authors are relating the characters to various components. The three things that are most necessary for life are air, water, and light, and *Jaya*’s most significant figures are related to those three things. This demonstrates the authors’ interest in

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including nature in the narrative. Only by maintaining a healthy balance with our surroundings, one can lead a harmonious life.

Conclusion

Eco-criticism can help uncover ecological themes and messages embedded in the novel and shed light on how they have influenced the cultural and environmental consciousness of the Indian subcontinent. By examining the portrayal of human nature relationship one can understand the ecological aspect of these ancient texts and their enduring relevance in contemporary discussion of environmental sustainability and ethics. Nature works through its character teachings and narrative the Epic provides valuable insight into the interconnectedness of humanity and nature offering lessons that continue to resonate in the discussion of environmental ethics and sustainability. The consequence of human actions on the natural world is evidenced in the novel the destruction of the Khandava forest was equal to the destruction caused in the Kurukshetra war.

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